

Paper 1

**IMPACT OF COVID -19 ON ‘HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS’ BEHAVIOUR
AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS LEARNING IN QATAR’**

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ABSTRACT

The world has witnessed a sudden change in all aspects of the human being especially learning style of the students and their behavior due to the COVID19. The pandemic has led to the adoption of particular hygienic behavior (e.g., Keeping distance, Wearing masks, Washing hands), discouraged certain daily practices (e.g., Leaving home, shaking hands) and also encouraged the new style of learning pattern (from Physical classes to Remote classes). The curriculum transaction through online medium has been a recent modification brought out by the education system worldwide in the wake of the current pandemic situation. I have conducted a study on ‘**Impact of COVID-19 on High School Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning in Qatar**’. The action research study identifies the major behavioral problems and attitude towards learning through proper analysis and suggesting the appropriate remedies. The results of my study is presented with suitable assessment by using various digital tools such as Mente.com, Google form, and Padlet.com. I have considered students of class IX to XII to collect the data and analyze the result based on the response given by them. I have also considered gender and Age as well.

Introduction:

COVID-19 proved a pandemic that has affected the whole world on a large scale. Every walk of life got disturbed by this pandemic. COVID-19 not only affected the political, social, and religious activities but also resulted in the Students’ learning and behavior. Students, parents and teachers were unable to cope with a sudden change and they gradually got adjusted through various processes of Orientations organized by the Ministry of Education and Higher Education and Schools. The Ministry of Education and Higher Education Ministry of Qatar decided to provide blended education to students from September 2020 and ensured 30% of students

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attending physical classes following COVID protocol released by the Ministry of Education and Higher Education. All Indian schools strictly followed the guidelines and provided safe atmosphere and ensured maximum no.of students’ attendance. The ministry monitored the process and advised all the schools to ensure quality education. Approximately 50 to 60% of students attended physical classes and 100% of them attended Remote classes. Later, in November 2020: all schools were instructed to increase the students’ participation in physical classes from 30% to 42% and ensured quality education with no compromise and administered physical examination for higher classes by following Protocol. Even though all governments worldwide decided to continue either Remote Learning or blended education approximately a billion students are currently affected by school closures or partial education in response to the pandemic.

Based on the data collected through various sources such as Google form, interview and online interactions with Students I am able to draw result and impact of COVID -19 on Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning.

Objectives:

The objectives of this research study include the following.

1. To study the impact of COVID-19 on Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning.
2. To determine the various aspects of developing unacceptable or acceptable behavior and positive/negative attitude towards learning.
3. To recommend possible solutions to promote a positive and healthy atmosphere for students at home and school.

Methodology

Data were collected through Google form to assess various parameters of Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning. The respondents included 184 students of classes IX to XII belonging to various age groups between 13 and 18 years and the category of male and female. The questionnaire consisted of 20 multiple-choice questions to study the impact of COVID-19. The respondents were asked to attempt all the questions regarding the effect of COVID-19 in their daily life categorized as two areas such as behavior and learning.

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Data Analysis

The survey questionnaire was used for data collection. Data was collected by using Google form as mode of delivery and the survey instrument was online. The responses were collected in the month of December 2020. All the data collected was organized, cleaned and then analyzed properly. The data were classified using the self-cognitive classifier to analyze its auto and cross correlation. The data analysis uses the frequency procedure to tabulate the counts and calculate the percentages of responses. The information retrieved from the analysis gives the probabilistic predicted behavior during COVID-19. The quantitative and qualitative data were then graphically represented in the form of graphs and charts to illustrate relationships between various data elements.

Result and Summary

52.3% of the respondents participating in the study were females and 47.7% were males.

Gender – Male /Female

65.3% of the respondents participating in the research study were reported belonging to the age group 14-16 years, while as 34.7% belonging to the age group 16-18 years.

Age Group

Are you studying your subject with interest in the remote platform?

69.4 % of respondents consider remote platform for studying their subjects with interest, while 30.6% consider remote platform is not helping them to study with interest. It shows that the majority of respondents prefer remote classes for joyful learning with interest.

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Would you prefer attending your revision session in the physical classroom?

61.7% of respondents consider physical classes for their revision session as part of preparation for CBSE board examination, while 38.3% consider remote classes for their revision session. It shows that physical classes are required for getting individual attention for effective revision sessions.

Has COVID 19 affected your Systematic Study?

72.5% of respondents say that COVID 19 affected their systematic study, while 27.5% say that pandemic situation is not affecting their systematic study. This result shows that the majority of respondents prefer physical classes to make their study systematic.

Do you feel that Remote Learning affected your Writing Skill?

55.4% of respondents say that Remote Learning does not affect their writing skill, while 44.6% reflect their problem of affecting writing skill due to remote sessions.

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Has your anxiety/stress level increased in the case of studies during the COVID-19 pandemic situation?

73.6% of respondents say that anxiety or stress level regarding studies has increased their during COVID 19 pandemic situation, while 26.4% of respondents reported that it did not affect their anxiety or stress. It shows that, the anxiety/stress level of majority respondents has increased in the case of studies during the pandemic situation.

Do you feel that your confidence level in using digital learning tools has improved?

81.3% of respondents say that confidence level of using digital learning tools has improved due to remote session, while 18.7% reports that their confidence level of using digital tools has no improvement.

Do you feel that COVID 19 affected your attitude towards the completion of assignment?

61.1% of respondents reported that COVID 19 affected in developing a positive attitude towards the completion of assignment and 38.9% of respondents reported it did not affected them in developing a negative attitude towards the completion of assignment. It shows that COVID 19 affected Students' attitude in developing a positive attitude towards the completion of assignment.

Has COVID -19 affected your sleeping pattern?

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61.7% of respondents reported that COVID 19 affected their sleeping patterns, while 38.3% reported that it did not affect their sleeping pattern. It shows that the majority of respondents missed their normal sleeping patterns.

Do you feel worried after watching any kind of information (COVID- 19 related) circulated on Media?

56% of respondents reported that they were worried after watching any kind of information (COVID- 19 related) circulated on media while others (44%) responded that they did not worry after watching any information.

Do you wash your hands to protect yourself from COVID-19 infection?

Almost all (95.3%) respondents reported that they developed a habit of washing hands to protect themselves from COVID-19 infection. It shows that all are much health conscious and aware about the consequences and it reflects behavioral changes and approached towards their life style.

Do you wear masks to protect yourself from COVID -19 infection?

98.4% of respondents reported that they regularly wear mask to protect themselves from COVID-19 infection. It also shows that COVID-19 changed everybody’s lifestyle and approach.

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Has COVID -19 affected your Physical Exercise?

58% of respondents reported that COVID 19 affected their physical exercise, while 42% reported that it did not affect them. It shows that COVID-19 affected most of the respondents' physical fitness and automatically it affects their mental fitness as well.

Are you worried about your higher education Due to COVID 19?

71% of respondents reported that they are very much worried about their higher education due to COVID 19, while 29% of respondents are not at all worried about their higher education. It shows that the pandemic affected their mind and thoughts on career hope or higher education opportunities due to the COVID-19.

Do you feel that COVID -19 affected your Inter personal skill and Communication?

57% of respondents reported that COVID 19 affected their inter personal skill and communication, while 43% reported that it did not affect their skill and communication. It shows that COVID 19 related lock down and protocol affected the majority respondents' personal skill and communication and it also shows that it reflects their personality and relationship with others and community.

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Did COVID 19 situation affect your social life considerably?

73.1% of respondents reported that COVID 19 affected their social life considerably, while 26.9% reported that it did not affect their social life. It shows that the pandemic affected social life of majority respondents

Result Analysis

SL NO	Questions	Response	
		Yes	No
01	Are you studying your subject with interest in the remote platform?	30.6%	69.4%
02	Would you prefer attending your revision session in the physical classroom?	61.7%	38.3%
03	Has COVID-19 affected your Systematic Study?	72.5%	27.5%
04	Do you feel that Remote Learning affected your Writing Skill?	55.4%	44.6%
05	Do you feel that your confidence level in using digital learning tools has improved?	81.3%	18.7%
06	Do you feel that COVID-19 affected your attitude towards the completion of assignment?	61.1%	38.9%
07	Has your anxiety/stress level increased in the case of studies during COVID-19 pandemic situation?	73.6%	26.4%
		62.13%	38% %

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SL NO	Questions	Response	
		Yes	No
08	Has COVID-19 affected your sleeping pattern?	61.7%	38.3%
09	Do you feel worried after watching any information (COVID- 19 related) circulated on Media?	56%	44%
10	Do you wash your hands to protect yourself from COVID-19 infection?	95.3%	4.7%
11	Do you wear masks to protect yourself from COVID-19 infection?	98.4%	1.6%
12	Has COVID-19 affected your Physical Exercise?	58%	42%
13	Are you worried about your higher education due to COVID-19?	71%	29%
14	Do you feel that COVID-19 affected your Inter-personal skill and Communication?	57%	43%
15	Did COVID-19 situation affect your social life considerably?	73.1%	26.9%
		71.31	28.68

The average percent 62.13 of total score against the answer ‘YES’ shows that the COVID-19 affected the respondents, while average percent 38 of total score against answer ‘NO’ shows that COVID-19 did not affect the respondents.

The average percent 71.31 of total scores against the answer ‘YES’ shows that the COVID-19 affected the respondents, while average % 28.68 of total score against answer ‘NO’ shows that COVID-19 did not affect the respondents.

Findings:

1. COVID-19 affected majority students’ a revision study, revision sessions, systematic study, writing skill and completion of assignments and increased their anxiety and stress.
2. The confidence level of Students’ using digital tools for learning has improved due to remote classes.
3. COVID-19 affected majority of students’ sleeping patterns, developing worries on higher education, physical exercise, interpersonal skill, communication and social life.
4. Due to COVID, students became well aware and conscious about their health and started wearing masks, washing hands regularly.
5. The impact of COVID-19 affected Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning even-

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though they obtained digital skills and developed a mind of health conscious.

Recommendations:

1. All educational institutions must organize various programs for students such as awareness, counseling and physical and health activities to make them more flexible and cope with the current situation.
2. Students need to be encouraged to attend physical classes according to the guidelines of the Ministry of Education and Higher Education so that students develop a positive attitude towards learning and develop a positive rapport towards peers and teachers and it will help them release their stress and worries.
3. Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning are correlated. If a student is aware of the situation and improving interpersonal skill & communication with a high level of Confidence it will boost their positive attitude towards learning and excel their result.
4. The involvement of parents and community needs to be ensured and special program for them also needs to be organized.
5. Personalized Learning needs to be encouraged and individual support needs to be provided.
6. Screen time for remote learning is to be minimized and less number of assignments need to be given.
7. The personal interaction with teachers and Peers needs to be scheduled.

Conclusion:

The study investigates the impact of COVID-19 on Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning. The average score shows that Students’ behavior and their attitude towards learning are correlated. A positive behavior helps students develop a positive attitude towards leaning. The objectives are achieved through qualitative assessment on the data collected and the results represented became the basis for suggesting the suitable recommendations.

The result analysis determines a negative impact of COVID-19 on majority Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning. The assessment and subsequent analysis on the data collected through the online survey convey that the lack of physical activity, lack of proper sleeping patterns and unwanted worries and anxiety affect students’ attitude towards learning and it results in developing a low level of confidence about their higher education and career. The result analysis also determines that the current pandemic situation has a negative impact on students’

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completion of assignments, systematic study and interpersonal skills even though students obtain a high level of confidence in using digital tools for effective learning. Although this research study has some limitations like less number of responses through a Google form, it can be helpful in understanding the impact of COVID-19 on Students’ behavior and attitude towards learning.

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